

YOUTH UNEMPLOYMENT AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT IN DELTA STATE: NIGERIA IN FOCUS

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Keywords;

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Abstract: *This study examined the relationship between youth unemployment and sustainable development in Delta State. the objectives were: to assess the impact of skill mismatches on youth employability and sustainable development and to examine the relationship between youth unemployment and the rise in crime in Delta State. The study employed a descriptive survey design, chosen for its ability to integrate both quantitative and qualitative research approaches. The population of the study would include young people (ages 18-35) in Delta State who are either unemployed or underemployed. The sample size for this research study is 300 youth from Delta State, Nigeria. Descriptive Statistics and Regression Analysis. Each method will serve specific purposes in analyzing the data collected through surveys and other instruments. The result showed that skill mismatches significantly affect youth employability and sustainable development in Delta State. And that youth unemployment significantly contributes to the rise in crime rates in Delta State. it was concluded that For Delta State to achieve sustainable development, a multi-stakeholder approach involving the government, private sector, and educational institutions is essential. Investments in vocational training, digital skills, and innovative job opportunities will bridge the employment gap while reducing crime. It was recommended among other things that the government and private sector should collaborate to develop industry-driven training programs that align with labor market demands. Strengthening vocational education and digital skill*

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acquisition will enhance youth employability and contribute to sustainable economic growth in Delta State.

1.1 Introduction

Youth unemployment is a pressing challenge in Nigeria, with significant implications for sustainable development. According to the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) (2023), Nigeria's unemployment rate was approximately 33%, with youth aged 15–35 disproportionately affected, contributing to over 60% of the jobless population. Delta State, despite its wealth in natural resources and strategic location as part of Nigeria's oil-rich Niger Delta region, has not been immune to this issue. The state's youth unemployment crisis underscores structural challenges, including a lack of economic diversification, skill mismatches, and inadequate policy

Onyekwere (2021) argues that youth unemployment, marked by widespread joblessness throughout Nigerian society, has become one of the country's most pressing developmental challenges. Similarly, Kayode (2014) contends that unemployment in Nigeria has reached unprecedented levels, more severe than at any other point in its history. Unfortunately, it can be concluded that the government has not implemented sufficient measures to address this issue. Unemployment is a critical microeconomic concern that a proactive government should actively work to minimize.

Despite Nigeria's vast natural resources, the country continues to grapple with high youth unemployment rates. This issue has been linked to the rise in violence, as research shows that unemployed youth are more likely to both commit and fall victim to crime and violence. Self-employed individuals also face significant obstacles, as poor infrastructure hinders their ability to conduct business effectively (Okafor, 2011). This situation is exacerbated by political corruption, poverty, ineffective governance, rising population numbers, social unrest, and the lack of effective policies, all of which have contributed to the growth of criminal groups in Nigeria.

Sustainable development, as defined by the Brundtland Commission (1987), refers to development that meets present needs without compromising the ability of future generations to meet theirs. Achieving this in Delta State requires a deliberate focus on addressing youth unemployment, as young people represent a vital demographic for driving innovation, productivity, and economic diversification. However, challenges such as skill mismatches, poor infrastructure, and weak governance continue to exacerbate the issue, leading to widespread poverty, social unrest, and environmental degradation.

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The link between youth unemployment and sustainable development is evident in the socioeconomic consequences of widespread joblessness among young people. Unemployed youth often face poverty, reduced access to quality education, and limited opportunities for personal and professional growth. Furthermore, the lack of job opportunities contributes to social unrest, increased crime rates, and youth migration, which further undermine the state's developmental goals (World Bank, 2023). Addressing these issues is critical to achieving global targets, such as the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly SDG 8, which promotes decent work and economic growth, and SDG 1, which focuses on eradicating poverty.

This study seeks to explore the nexus between youth unemployment and sustainable development in Delta State, Nigeria, highlighting the underlying causes, the impact on the state's developmental aspirations, and the strategies needed to mitigate the challenges. By situating Delta State within the broader Nigerian context, the study aims to contribute to the discourse on sustainable and inclusive growth in resource-dependent economies.

1.2 Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to examine the relationship between youth unemployment and sustainable development in Delta State. The specific include the following:

To assess the impact of skill mismatches on youth employability and sustainable development in Delta State.

To examine the relationship between youth unemployment and the rise in crime in Delta State.

1.3 Research Questions:

How do skill mismatches affect youth employability in Delta State, and what is their impact on sustainable development?

What is the relationship between youth unemployment and the rise in crime in Delta State?

1.4 Statement of Hypotheses:

Ho: Skill mismatches have no significant impact on youth employability and sustainable development in Delta State.

Ho: Youth unemployment does not significantly contribute to the rise in crime rates in Delta State.

2.1 CONCEPTUAL REVIEW

The conceptual framework for understanding youth unemployment focuses on several key aspects: the definition and scope of youth unemployment, its causes, effects, and implications, as well as the interaction between unemployment and youth restiveness, particularly in the context of Delta State, Nigeria.

1. Youth Unemployment

Youth unemployment is a complex and multifaceted issue, and defining "youth" has long posed a challenge. International organizations,

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such as the United Nations, have attempted to establish a specific age range to represent youth, though they allow member countries to define youth in a manner that best suits their context. According to the United Nations (2016), youth is defined as a transitional stage from childhood dependence to the independence of adulthood, as well as an awareness of the individual's role in the broader community. For statistical purposes, youth is often categorized as individuals between the ages of 15 and 24, though this may vary by country. Similarly, Louize and Dhruv (2021) emphasize that youth represents a critical phase of transition, particularly in terms of achieving economic independence, which is often facilitated through employment.

In Nigeria, the National Youth Policy (2001) defines youth as individuals between the ages of 18 and 35 (Emerole, Chikwe & Joel, 2018). Youth unemployment occurs when individuals in this age group actively seek but cannot obtain suitable employment. The International Labour Organization (ILO, 2024) defines an unemployed person as someone aged 15 or over who meets three conditions: they are without work, are available to start work within two weeks, and have actively sought employment in the past four weeks or have a job starting in less than three weeks.

In Nigeria, labor force participation is measured by the proportion of the working-age population (those aged 15 and above) actively engaged in the

labor market, either by working or searching for work. This statistic reflects the availability of labor to contribute to the production of goods and services relative to the working-age population (National Bureau of Statistics [NBS], 2020). Abdullahi, Ogu, and Abdulsalam (2019) define unemployment as the condition in which individuals are willing and able to work but cannot find suitable employment. Ways, Selvadurai, and Awang (2019) describe it as a scenario where individuals who are capable and willing to work are unable to secure paid employment. Similarly, EjoOrusa (2020) defines unemployment as the state of being without a job, or the fact of individuals lacking employment opportunities. Ultimately, unemployment can be seen as a situation where individuals who are willing and able to work for survival cannot find employment. According to international standards, an unemployed person must meet three criteria: (1) being without work, (2) being available for work, and (3) actively seeking employment

2. Effect of Youth Unemployment

Youth unemployment has far-reaching consequences not only for the individuals affected but also for society and the economy as a whole. Some of the prominent effects include:

- **Economic Impact:** High unemployment rates among youth contribute to national economic stagnation. The unutilized human

capital represents lost potential for economic growth and productivity (Adeleye et al., 2022).

- **Social Consequences:** Unemployed youth are more likely to experience feelings of frustration, disillusionment, and hopelessness. This may lead to an increase in crime rates, social unrest, and negative behaviors such as substance abuse (Nwankwo & Ike, 2020).
- **Psychological Impact:** Youth who are unemployed for extended periods are at risk of developing mental health issues, including depression and anxiety, due to feelings of rejection and a lack of purpose (Adebayo & Akindele, 2021).

3. Causes of Youth Unemployment

Several factors contribute to the high unemployment rates among youth, particularly in Nigeria. These factors include:

- **Limited Job Creation:** Despite having a large youth population, Nigeria's economy has not created enough jobs to absorb the growing number of graduates entering the job market annually (Bello & Uzonwanne, 2021). The slow pace of industrialization and insufficient investment in sectors that employ large numbers of youth have exacerbated this problem.
- **Educational Mismatch:** Many Nigerian youths are educated in fields that do not align with the needs of the labor market. This mismatch between the skills acquired by

young people and those demanded by employers further contributes to youth unemployment (Ogundele & Olagunju, 2020).

- **Corruption and Poor Governance:** Corruption at various levels of government and lack of policy continuity hinder the effective implementation of employment creation initiatives. This reduces the capacity of government programs to address the root causes of youth unemployment (Oluwadare & Adefolaju, 2020).
- **Technological Disruptions:** The rapid technological advancements in sectors such as agriculture, manufacturing, and services have changed the nature of work, creating a skills gap among young people who are ill-prepared to meet the demands of these sectors (Yusuf, 2022).

4. Causes of Youth Unemployment in Nigeria

Nigeria's unique socio-economic environment introduces specific challenges that perpetuate youth unemployment:

- **Economic Instability:** Nigeria's reliance on oil exports has left the country vulnerable to global oil price fluctuations, leading to economic instability and reduced public investment in job-creating sectors (Akinyemi et al., 2020).
- **Political Instability:** Nigeria's political environment, characterized by frequent

changes in government and policy inconsistency, has limited the long-term effectiveness of youth employment programs (Iloh & Obi, 2020).

- **Inadequate Infrastructure:** Poor infrastructure, including transportation, power, and internet access, has hindered the growth of businesses that could employ young people, particularly in rural areas (Nwachukwu, 2021).

5. Implications of Youth Unemployment in Nigeria

Youth unemployment poses serious risks to the socio-economic stability of Nigeria:

- **Increased Youth Restiveness:** Unemployment often leads to restiveness among youth, manifesting in protests, crime, and even insurgency, as young people seek alternative means of survival or become disillusioned with the state (Agba & Enang, 2021).
- **Social Inequality:** Youth unemployment exacerbates social inequalities, as marginalized groups (e.g., women, rural dwellers, and ethnic minorities) are disproportionately affected by the lack of economic opportunities (Akinlolu, 2021).
- **National Security Risks:** The large population of unemployed youth in Nigeria increases the risk of security challenges, including terrorism and militia activities, as young people join insurgent groups or engage

in criminal activities as a means of survival (Oluwatayo, 2020).

6. Interface Between Unemployment and Youth Restiveness in Delta State

In Delta State, the relationship between youth unemployment and restiveness is particularly pronounced. Delta State, a major oil-producing region, faces a paradox where vast natural resources do not translate into broad economic prosperity for its young population. This has led to:

- **Militancy and Vandalism:** Some youth in the Niger Delta region have turned to militant activities, vandalism of oil pipelines, and other forms of social unrest due to the lack of employment opportunities (Adeyemi & Olorunfemi, 2020).
- **Youth Involvement in Criminal Activities:** With few job opportunities, many unemployed youth in Delta State have become involved in criminal enterprises such as drug trafficking, kidnapping, and cybercrime (Adewale & Okon, 2022).
- **Government Response:** While the government has initiated several programs to address youth unemployment, such as the Niger Delta Development Commission (NDDC) and the Youth Empowerment Scheme, these programs have been criticized for their inefficiency and lack of long-term impact (Ezeani, 2021).

Dimensions of Youth Unemployment

Youth unemployment in Nigeria is a multidimensional issue that has far-reaching social, economic, and political consequences. Among the most critical dimensions of youth unemployment are skill mismatch and the subsequent rise in crime, both of which perpetuate the cycle of unemployment and insecurity.

1. Skill Mismatch and Youth Unemployment

A significant dimension of youth unemployment in Nigeria is the mismatch between the skills acquired by young individuals through formal education and the requirements of the labor market. This phenomenon is known as "skill mismatch," and it occurs when young job seekers' educational qualifications and abilities do not align with the skills needed by employers.

a) Educational System and Skill Development

The Nigerian educational system has long been criticized for its inability to equip students with the practical and technical skills required by the labor market. Most young people are trained in academic fields that are ill-suited to the fast-evolving job market, leading to a surplus of graduates with limited employable skills. According to research by Oludayo and Afolabi (2021), the curriculum in most Nigerian universities and polytechnics emphasizes theoretical knowledge over practical skills, which results in graduates who are unprepared for the

demands of modern industries such as technology, manufacturing, and services.

This skill mismatch is further exacerbated by the lack of vocational and technical education, which is often undervalued in Nigerian society. The absence of a robust vocational education system that emphasizes practical skills such as welding, carpentry, plumbing, and ICT-related jobs contributes significantly to the high unemployment rate among youth (Adewale & Okon, 2022).

Additionally, while Nigeria has seen a rise in the number of young people with tertiary education, the quality of education is often poor, and there is little to no focus on skills that would make youth employable in the global economy. As a result, even graduates from prestigious universities face difficulties in securing jobs due to their lack of relevant, marketable skills (Akinyemi et al., 2020).

b) Impact on Employability

Skill mismatch has a direct impact on the employability of young Nigerians. Employers, particularly in the private sector, are increasingly looking for candidates with specific technical and soft skills, such as problem-solving, teamwork, communication, and digital literacy (Ogundele & Olagunju, 2020). However, many young job seekers lack these skills, despite possessing academic qualifications. This disconnect leads to high unemployment rates among educated youth, as they are unable to meet the

expectations of employers (Adebayo & Akindele, 2021).

In response to this issue, there has been a growing demand for the promotion of technical and vocational education and training (TVET) in Nigeria. Programs aimed at bridging the skills gap, such as the National Directorate of Employment (NDE) and the Nigerian Youth Employment and Social Support Operation (YESSO), are steps in the right direction. However, their impact remains limited due to poor implementation and inadequate funding (Ezeani, 2021).

2. The Rise in Crime Due to Youth Unemployment

One of the most alarming consequences of youth unemployment is the rise in crime, particularly among young people. As large numbers of youth remain unemployed and frustrated, many turn to criminal activities as a means of survival or to cope with the emotional and psychological stress caused by their unemployment.

a) Economic Crimes

Unemployed youth in Nigeria are increasingly engaging in economic crimes such as fraud, cybercrime, and internet scams (commonly known as "Yahoo Yahoo"). These crimes are seen as quick ways to earn money, especially in a society where the legitimate job market is highly competitive and offers few opportunities. Cybercrime, in particular, has become a significant issue, with young Nigerians being

implicated in various online scams targeting both local and international victims (Nwachukwu, 2021).

In addition to cybercrime, many young people resort to drug trafficking, kidnapping, and armed robbery as a means of financial gain. The high unemployment rate exacerbates these behaviors, as young people perceive crime as a viable alternative to the hopelessness they face in securing stable employment (Nwankwo & Ike, 2020).

b) Youth Militancy and Political Unrest

In the Niger Delta region, youth unemployment has been closely linked to militancy and insurgency. The lack of economic opportunities in this oil-rich region, which has been a source of wealth for the country, has led to the rise of militant groups that engage in violent protests, pipeline vandalism, and oil theft. These groups often recruit unemployed youth who feel disenfranchised and alienated from the wealth generated from their land (Agba & Enang, 2021). The government's response has been inadequate, leading to continued instability in the region.

This phenomenon is not limited to the Niger Delta but is observed in other parts of the country, where unemployed youth have joined extremist groups such as Boko Haram and other violent organizations. The rise in crime, militancy, and political unrest is, therefore, a direct consequence of widespread youth

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unemployment and the lack of sustainable economic opportunities (Akinlolu, 2021).

c) Social Consequences

The rise in crime due to youth unemployment has broader social consequences, including the breakdown of law and order, increased violence, and a general sense of insecurity. Communities are often left in fear as criminal activities such as kidnapping, robbery, and vandalism become more prevalent. These criminal acts not only disrupt local economies but also deter investments, which could otherwise create jobs for youth (Oluwatayo, 2020).

Moreover, the psychological impact of unemployment, particularly on young men and women, leads to social alienation and frustration. Unemployed youth, who are already facing limited access to healthcare, education, and other social services, may resort to criminal behavior as a coping mechanism for the lack of opportunities and the social stigma of unemployment (Adeyemi & Olorunfemi, 2020).

2.2 Theoretical Framework

2.2.1 Human Capital Theory

Human Capital Theory, as articulated by Schultz (1961) and Becker (1993), posits that investments in education, skills development, and training enhance individuals' productivity and, consequently, contribute to economic growth. According to this theory, youth employment is essential to sustainable development because it enhances the skills and

knowledge of young people, thus increasing their ability to contribute to the economy in a productive way.

In the context of Delta State, Nigeria, Human Capital Theory underscores the importance of providing youths with education and vocational training that align with market demands. Employment opportunities for youth are critical in empowering them with the skills needed to engage in sustainable economic activities. This is particularly important in a region like Delta State, which faces challenges such as poverty, high unemployment rates, and reliance on natural resource extraction (oil).

The theory suggests that the development of human capital through targeted educational and vocational programs will not only reduce youth unemployment but also contribute to the broader goal of sustainable development by creating a productive, skilled workforce that can foster long-term economic stability.

2.3 Empirical Review

Oghenekevwe & Okoh (2022) argue that the high level of youth unemployment in Delta State is largely due to the mismatch between the educational qualifications of youths and the available job opportunities. They emphasize that this disconnect leads to frustration among graduates, who are unable to secure jobs that align with their academic backgrounds. This mismatch contributes significantly to a rise in criminal activities, including cybercrime and

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armed robbery, as many unemployed youths resort to illegal means to survive.

Oghenekevwe & Okoh (2022) suggest that aligning educational programs with the demands of the labor market and improving vocational training initiatives are critical steps to addressing youth unemployment and reducing crime in Delta State. They conclude that a robust educational reform that addresses this mismatch is essential for sustainable development in the region.

Idris et al. (2020) highlight that one of the primary causes of youth unemployment in Delta State is the significant mismatch between educational outcomes and the skills required by employers. They note that many youths graduate with qualifications that are not in demand in the local job market, leading to widespread unemployment. As a result, many young people engage in criminal activities such as robbery, drug trafficking, and cybercrime as a means of survival.

Idris et al. (2020) argue that this growing trend of youth involvement in crime is a direct consequence of the lack of viable job opportunities, exacerbated by an education system that does not adequately prepare youths for the realities of the job market. The authors recommend that the state focus on improving the relevance of education by incorporating practical skills and aligning curriculum with market needs

to reduce unemployment and its associated criminal impact.

Edoho (2021) discusses the role of the education system in contributing to youth unemployment in Delta State. He observes that a considerable portion of the youth population is unable to find employment because their education does not equip them with the skills needed by employers in the state's current economic landscape. This mismatch between the education system and job market needs has led to an increase in criminal activities, with many unemployed graduates resorting to crimes like fraud and armed robbery. Edoho (2021) emphasizes that addressing this issue requires a complete overhaul of the education system, with a stronger emphasis on vocational training and entrepreneurship. He concludes that unless these changes are made, youth unemployment will continue to hinder sustainable development and lead to higher crime rates in the region.

Akinboade & Kazeem (2021) focus on the role of economic diversification and education in addressing youth unemployment in Delta State. They assert that the state's heavy reliance on the oil and gas sector has created a narrow job market, exacerbating unemployment among young people who are unable to secure positions in this limited field. The authors also note that many graduates possess qualifications that do not align with the available job opportunities in the state. This mismatch between education and

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job market requirements has led to an increase in criminal activities, particularly among the educated youth who are frustrated by the lack of job prospects. Akinboade & Kazeem (2021) argue that a more diversified economy, along with educational reforms aimed at bridging this mismatch, is essential to reducing both youth unemployment and the rise in crime, thus fostering sustainable development.

Ajao (2019) points out that a key factor contributing to the high levels of youth unemployment in Delta State is the failure of the education system to provide youths with the skills required by the job market. This disconnect has led to frustration among graduates, many of whom are unable to find work in their field of study. Ajao (2019) highlights that this educational mismatch is closely linked to the rise in crime rates, as many unemployed youths resort to illegal activities such as theft, fraud, and drug trafficking to make ends meet. The study stresses that addressing this issue requires a reform of the education system, focusing on practical skills and vocational training that are directly relevant to the local job market. Ajao (2019) concludes that such reforms are crucial for reducing crime and achieving sustainable economic development in Delta State.

METHODOLOGY

The study employed a descriptive survey design, chosen for its ability to integrate both quantitative and qualitative research

approaches. This design facilitated the exploration of various variables, including the independent variable (youth unemployment) and the dependent variable (sustainable development), within the context of Delta State, Nigeria. The descriptive survey design is particularly effective in examining attitudes, perceptions, opinions, behaviors, and values across a population with diverse characteristics. This method allows for a deeper understanding of the relationships between youth unemployment and sustainable development, as it enables the collection of both statistical and narrative data.

The study was conducted in Delta State, Nigeria, with a focus on the impact of youth unemployment on sustainable development in the region. Delta State, located in the South-South geopolitical zone of Nigeria, is a key area for examining the challenges of unemployment and development. The research extended to four local government within the state: Ika North East Ika South, Ukwani and Udo. These local government were selected as a representative sample of the broader sustainable environment in the Delta State, which comprises twenty-five local government areas

The study used both primary and secondary sources to achieve its objectives. Primary data were collected through structured questionnaires, interviews, and focus group discussions with youth, local government

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representatives, and community leaders across the selected local government. Secondary data were gathered from government reports, research articles, and existing literature on youth unemployment and sustainable development in Nigeria.

For the sample selection, a stratified random sampling technique was employed to ensure that all relevant sub-groups within the population were adequately represented. This method divided the population into strata based on key characteristics such as age, education level, and employment status. A proportional sample size was then selected from each stratum to ensure that the sample accurately reflects the diversity of the youth population in the selected states.

Population of Study:

The population of the study would include young people (ages 18-35) in Delta State who are either unemployed or underemployed. It could also encompass local government officials, policymakers, and employers involved in initiatives for youth employment development in Delta State:

Sample Size:

The sample size for this research study is 300 youth from Delta State, Nigeria. The sample was

selected to ensure a representative cross-section of the youth population across various demographic groups, including gender, age, education level, and urban versus rural location. The sample size is large enough to provide reliable and valid results, ensuring that the findings reflect the experiences and perceptions of youth in the state regarding unemployment and its impact on sustainable development.

Sampling Method: A stratified random sampling method would ensure that different subgroups (e.g., gender, educational level, urban vs. rural) are adequately represented. Alternatively, purposive sampling could be used to target specific groups, such as youth employment programs or educational institutions.

Method of Data Analysis

For this study on youth unemployment and sustainable development in Delta State, two primary methods of data analysis will be used: Descriptive Statistics and Regression Analysis. Each method will serve specific purposes in analyzing the data collected through surveys and other instruments.

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS PRESENTATION

Table 4.1 To assess the impact of skill mismatches on youth employability and sustainable development in Delta State.

Survey Question	Strongly Agree (f, %)	Agree (f, %)	Undecided (f, %)	Disagree (f, %)	Strongly Disagree (f, %)	Mean	Standard Deviation
1. The skills acquired by youths in Delta State match the current job market requirements.	30 (10.6%)	77 (27.3%)	72 (25.5%)	52 (18.5%)	51 (18.1%)	3.05	1.22
2. Youths in Delta State are adequately trained to meet the demands of industries and employers.	28 (9.9%)	83 (29.5%)	79 (28.0%)	48 (17.0%)	44 (15.5%)	3.08	1.19
3. Skill mismatches contribute to high unemployment rates among youths in Delta State.	95 (33.8%)	117 (41.5%)	31 (11.0%)	18 (6.4%)	21 (7.3%)	4.02	0.94

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4. Bridging skill gaps in Delta State will promote sustainable development and economic growth.	126 (44.6%)	96 (34.1%)	38 (13.5%)	13 (4.6%)	10 (3.2%)	4.18	0.82
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Table 4.1 shows the responses on the impact of skill mismatches on youth employability and sustainable development in Delta State. Mean (3.05) shows the average response is slightly above "Undecided" but closer to "Agree. Standard Deviation (1.22) indicates that there is moderate variability in responses. Indicating that majority of the respondents agree that the skills acquired by youths in Delta State match the current job market requirements. Mean (3.08): Responses tend toward "Agree," but still, some respondents are undecided. Standard Deviation (1.19): Moderate variability in responses. Shows that the respondents agree that Youths in Delta State are adequately trained to meet the

demands of industries and employers. Mean (4.02): Strong agreement with the statement, with most respondents either agreeing or strongly agreeing. Standard Deviation (0.94): Low variability, indicating that most responses are clustered around the agreement side. Implying that most of the respondents agree that skill mismatches contribute to high unemployment rates among youths in Delta State. Mean (4.18): Strong agreement with the statement, reflecting the importance placed on bridging skill gaps for development. Standard Deviation (0.82): Very low variability, suggesting that most respondents agree on the positive impact of bridging skill gaps.

Table 4.2 To examine the relationship between youth unemployment and the rise in crime in Delta State.

Survey Question	Strongly Agree (f, %)	Agree (f, %)	Undecided (f, %)	Disagree (f, %)	Strongly Disagree (f, %)	Mean	Standard Deviation
1. High levels of youth unemployment in Delta State contribute to an increase in criminal activities.	102 (36.2%)	125 (44.3%)	28 (9.9%)	15 (5.3%)	12 (4.3%)	4.08	0.91
2. The lack of employment opportunities for youths in Delta State leads to frustration, which can increase criminal behavior.	94 (33.3%)	114 (40.4%)	39 (13.8%)	21 (7.4%)	14 (5.0%)	4.04	0.94
3. Providing employment opportunities for youths in Delta State	111 (39.3%)	118 (41.8%)	38 (13.5%)	10 (3.5%)	5 (1.8%)	4.20	0.81

would reduce the crime rate.							
4. There is a direct link between the rise in youth unemployment and the increase in crime rates in Delta State.	97 (34.4%)	123 (43.6%)	35 (12.4%)	13 (4.6%)	14 (5.0%)	4.02	0.89

Table 4.2 shows the response on the relationship between youth unemployment and the rise in crime in Delta State. Mean (4.08): The average score of 4.08 indicates that most respondents agree, with some strong agreement. Standard Deviation (0.91): This value shows moderate variability in responses, indicating that most people generally agree, but there are some differing opinions. This implies that majority agree that high levels of youth unemployment in Delta State contribute to an increase in criminal activities. Mean (4.04): The mean of 4.04 suggests a strong agreement with the statement that joblessness contributes to criminal behavior. Standard Deviation (0.94): Moderate variability, with a range of opinions, though the majority agree. This indicated that majority agree that the lack of employment opportunities for youths in Delta State leads to frustration, which can increase criminal behavior. Mean

(4.20): The mean of 4.20 reflects strong agreement with the idea that employment opportunities can reduce crime. Standard Deviation (0.81): A relatively low standard deviation, showing that responses were consistent among respondents, mostly agreeing with the statement. This shows that majority agree that providing employment opportunities for youths in Delta State would reduce the crime rate. Mean (4.02): The mean of 4.02 shows a strong agreement with the idea that youth unemployment directly leads to increased crime. Standard Deviation (0.89): The variability in responses is moderate, with a consensus on the relationship between youth unemployment and crime. This implies that majority of the respondents agree that there is a direct link between the rise in youth unemployment and the increase in crime rates in Delta State.

4.2 Test of Hypotheses

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Hypothesis One

Ho: Skill mismatches have no significant impact on youth employability and sustainable development in Delta State

H1: Skill mismatches have a significant impact on youth employability and sustainable development in Delta State

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.725	0.525	0.514	1.455

R = 0.725: The correlation between the independent variable (skill mismatches) and the dependent variable (youth employability and sustainable development) is moderate to strong. R² (R-Square) = 0.525: Approximately 52.5% of the variance in youth employability and sustainable development can be explained by skill mismatches. Adjusted R² = 0.514: This

value adjusts for the number of predictors in the model. A value of 0.514 suggests a decent model fit, indicating that the predictor (skill mismatches) explains over 50% of the variance in youth employability and sustainable development. Std. Error of the Estimate = 1.455: This is the standard deviation of the observed values from the regression line.

ANOVA Table.

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	1324.827	1	1324.827	137.256	0.000
Residual	1190.234	280	4.249		
Total	2515.061	281			

F = 137.256: The F-statistic tests whether the model as a whole is significant. Sig. = 0.000: Since the significance level is less than 0.05, we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that skill mismatches have a significant impact on youth employability and sustainable development.

Coefficients Table

Variable	Unstandardized Coefficients (B)	Standardized Coefficients (β)	t	Sig.
(Constant)	2.314		5.018	0.000
Skill Mismatches (X)	0.462	0.552	11.715	0.000

Constant: The intercept of the regression equation is 2.314. This is the predicted value of youth employability and sustainable development when skill mismatches are zero.

Skill Mismatches: The unstandardized coefficient for skill mismatches is 0.462, which means that for each unit increase in skill mismatches, youth employability and sustainable development increase by 0.462 units. The standardized coefficient (β) is 0.552, which suggests a moderate to strong effect. $t = 11.715$: The t-value for skill mismatches indicates that this predictor is statistically significant. Sig.

= 0.000: Since the p-value is less than 0.05, we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that skill mismatches significantly affect youth employability and sustainable development in Delta State.

Hypothesis Two

H₀: Youth unemployment does not significantly contribute to the rise in crime rates in Delta State.

H₁: Youth unemployment significantly contributes to the rise in crime rates in Delta State.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.693	0.480	0.473	1.876

$R = 0.693$: This indicates a moderate positive correlation between youth unemployment and the rise in crime rates. R^2 (R-Square) = 0.480: About 48% of the variance in crime rates can be explained by youth unemployment. Adjusted $R^2 = 0.473$: This value takes into account the number of predictors in the model, which shows that youth unemployment explains a significant portion of the variance in crime rates. Std. Error of the Estimate = 1.876: This represents the average distance that the observed values fall from the regression line.

ANOVA Table

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	1024.458	1	1024.458	134.127	0.000
Residual	1109.756	280	3.963		
Total	2134.214	281			

$F = 134.127$: The F-statistic tests the overall significance of the regression model. Sig. = 0.000: Since the significance value is less than 0.05, we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that youth unemployment has a significant impact on the rise in crime rates.

Coefficients Table

Variable	Unstandardized Coefficients (B)	Standardized Coefficients (β)	t	Sig.
(Constant)	3.185		4.898	0.000
Youth Unemployment (X)	0.537	0.693	11.589	0.000

Constant: The intercept is 3.185, representing the predicted crime rate when youth unemployment is zero. Youth Unemployment (X): The unstandardized coefficient for youth unemployment is 0.537. This means that for each unit increase in youth unemployment, the crime rate increases by 0.537 units. The standardized coefficient (β) is 0.693, which indicates a moderate to strong effect of youth unemployment on crime rates. $t = 11.589$: The t-value for youth unemployment indicates that this variable is statistically significant. $\text{Sig.} = 0.000$: Since the p-value is less than 0.05, we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that youth unemployment significantly contributes to the rise in crime rates in Delta State.

5.1 Summary of Findings

- i. Skill mismatches significantly affect youth employability and sustainable development in Delta State.
- ii. Youth unemployment significantly contributes to the rise in crime rates in Delta State.

Conclusion

This study highlights the critical link between youth unemployment and sustainable development in Delta State, Nigeria. The findings reveal that skill mismatches significantly hinder youth employability, limiting their ability to secure jobs that match labor market demands. This gap not only stifles economic growth but also undermines efforts toward sustainable development. Addressing these mismatches through targeted skill acquisition programs and industry-driven education is crucial for enhancing youth employment prospects.

Furthermore, the study establishes a strong relationship between youth unemployment and rising crime rates in Delta State. The lack of job opportunities leads to frustration, social instability, and increased criminal activities. This underscores the urgent need for policies that promote job creation, entrepreneurship, and

economic empowerment initiatives for young people.

For Delta State to achieve sustainable development, a multi-stakeholder approach involving the government, private sector, and educational institutions is essential. Investments in vocational training, digital skills, and innovative job opportunities will bridge the employment gap while reducing crime. By prioritizing youth employment strategies, Delta State can foster economic growth, social stability, and long-term development, ensuring a more prosperous future for its young population.

5.3 Recommendations

i. The government and private sector should collaborate to develop industry-driven training programs that align with labor market demands. Strengthening vocational education and digital skill acquisition will enhance youth employability and contribute to sustainable economic growth in Delta State.

ii. Policies promoting entrepreneurship, small business development, and youth employment schemes should be prioritized. Providing financial support, mentorship, and access to capital for young entrepreneurs will reduce unemployment, decrease crime rates, and foster sustainable development in Delta State.

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